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The Nicotinic Acetylcholine Receptor and Its Pentameric Homologs: Toward an Allosteric Mechanism of Signal Transduction at the Atomic Level

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Keywords

synaptic receptors, allosteric regulation, nicotinic acetylcholine receptor, signal transduction mechanism, neuropharmacology, brain disorders

Abstract

The nicotinic acetylcholine receptor has served, since its biochemical identification in the 1970s, as a model of an allosteric ligand-gated ion channel mediating signal transition at the synapse. In recent years, the application of X-ray crystallography and high-resolution cryo-electron microscopy, together with molecular dynamic simulations of nicotinic receptors and homologs, have opened a new era in the understanding of channel gating by the neurotransmitter. They reveal, at atomic resolution, the diversity and flexibility of the multiple ligand-binding sites, including recently discovered allosteric modulatory sites distinct from the neurotransmitter orthosteric site, and the conformational dynamics of the activation process as a molecular switch linking these multiple sites. The model emerging from these studies

paves the way for a new pharmacology based, first, upon the occurrence of an original mode of indirect allosteric modulation, distinct from a steric competition for a single and rigid binding site, and second, the design of drugs that specifically interact with privileged conformations of the receptor such as agonists, antagonists, and desensitizers. Research on nicotinic receptors is still at the forefront of understanding the mode of action of drugs on the nervous system.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Louis Pasteur (1, p. 138) recognized that the action of certain substances on the nervous system is mediated by defined components of the living matter and described, regarding the difference in taste of isomeric forms of sugars, a “dissymmetric active body that would play a role in the nervous impression.” This view was further elaborated by Paul Ehrlich (2) and most of all by John Newport Langley (3, p. 182) who sought to localize and specify the target of curare and nicotine in neuromuscular preparations and concluded that “the muscle substance which combines with nicotine or curari is not identical with the substance which contracts... I have called it the receptive substance;” this receptive substance is known today as the receptor.

It took almost 65 years to identify the first receptor for a neurotransmitter: the nicotinic acetylcholine receptor (nAChR) (4; reviewed in 5). This was made possible by the joint use of the electric organs of fish as a rich source of receptor and α -bungarotoxin (α -Bgtx), a snake venom toxin with exquisite specificity (6; reviewed in 5). Subsequent reconstitution studies showed that nAChR is an integral membrane protein with a molecular mass of approximately 290 kDa that possesses all the structural elements necessary to mediate the electric response to a synaptic pulse of $\sim 3 \times 10^{-4}$ M acetylcholine (ACh) on a millisecond timescale (motor endplate).

2. THE NICOTINIC ACETYLCHOLINE RECEPTOR: AN UNCONVENTIONAL ALLOSTERIC PROTEIN

Patch-clamp techniques revealed that the electric response represents a population of single square-shaped openings with a risetime in the microsecond range and a mean open duration of a few milliseconds. In addition, prolonged application of ACh or nicotine was found to block subsequent receptor responses, a process termed desensitization that was assumed to slowly (on a 100-ms-to-1-s timescale) stabilize a new high-affinity closed (refractory) state of the receptor referred to as desensitized (7–9).

An important step was the demonstration that these electrical phenomena have a structural basis. First, the data unambiguously showed that in native membrane fragments (155), the receptor is present in a state that binds cholinergic agonists with low affinity and that prolonged exposure to the agonist stabilizes the receptor, in a slow (seconds–minutes) and reversible manner, in a high-affinity state for agonists. Next, time-resolved rapid mixing techniques were developed with fluorescent agonists like dansyl-C6-choline (10) or isotopically labeled cholinergic ligands and rapid filtration (11), as well as changes in intrinsic or extrinsic fluorescence after labeling of the receptor with fluorescent probes (12, 13; see also the references in 14). Studies with dansyl-C6-choline and [³H]-ACh showed that, in addition to the slow desensitization on the second timescale, a faster conformational transition to an intermediate state called I (15) would occur with a rate constant of 2 s⁻¹ (16) to 50 s⁻¹ (17). Parallel functional studies using the same membrane preparation revealed that the transition to I fits with a fast desensitization of the response (15). A simple four-state model was found to be compatible with the concerted model for allosteric transitions (18) and that proposed by Katz & Thesleff (19) for desensitization (reviewed in 20).

To sum up, the *in vivo* and *in vitro* data demonstrate that the receptor protein interconverts between—at least—four discrete conformations: (*a*) a resting closed-channel state (R) stabilized by nicotinic antagonists; (*b*) an active, fast, open-channel state (A) with low affinity for ACh and nicotinic agonists; and (*c*) fast (I) and (*d*) slow (D) desensitized states with higher affinities for ACh and nicotinic agonists (but also for some antagonists). Contrary to an opinion widespread among pharmacologists, the highest-affinity states do not correspond to the active state of the receptor—far from it. In fact, the relatively low affinity of the active state permits fast and repetitive transmission (21, 22).

3. FUNCTIONAL ARCHITECTURE OF NICOTINIC ACETYLCHOLINE RECEPTORS

Early biochemical dissection of the isolated nAChR from fish electric organs (156) revealed that it spontaneously forms oligomers consisting of five homologous subunits with the arrangement $\alpha 1\text{-}\gamma\text{-}\alpha 1\text{-}\delta\text{-}\beta$. They are symmetrically arranged around a central ion channel, with a five-fold symmetry axis perpendicular to the membrane. The primary structure of each subunit established through protein sequencing and cDNA cloning and sequencing revealed a large hydrophilic amino-terminal extracellular domain (ECD), a transmembrane domain (TMD) consisting of four hydrophobic segments (M1–M4), and a variable hydrophilic intracellular domain (ICD). The ECD harbors two ACh-binding sites at the $\alpha 1\text{-}\delta$ and $\alpha 1\text{-}\gamma$ interfaces, which are functionally linked to the centrally located cationic channel in the TMD, almost 60 Å away (reviewed in 20–22). The gating of the ion channel by ACh that takes place between topographically distant sites is an unquestionable allosteric interaction. Moreover, the different conformations of the receptor, including the active state, have been observed even in the absence of ACh (23), validating the fundamental premise of the Monod–Wyman–Changeux (MWC) model (18) and ruling out an exclusive induced-fit mechanism. The nAChR protein thus possesses all the structural elements

required to convert a chemical signal into an electrical response and mediates the intercellular communication between neurons by acting as an allosteric switch (24).

There are 17 genes that code for nAChR subunits in the human genome, leading to an astronomical number of possible oligomeric combinations in pharmacologically distinct hetero- and homopentamers. However, the most represented compositions *in vivo* include the muscle-type $\alpha\beta\gamma\delta$ nAChR, the neuronal $\alpha 4\beta 2$ and $\alpha 3\beta 4$ nAChRs, and the homopentameric $\alpha 7$ nAChR. nAChRs belong to the superfamily of pentameric ligand-gated ion channels (pLGICs) present in bacteria and animals, which also includes the major mammalian neurotransmitter receptors for serotonin (5HT₃R), glycine (GlyR), and γ -aminobutyric acid (GABA_AR). nAChRs and 5HT₃R form a subfamily that mediates excitatory transmission; these receptors contain an ion channel selective for Na⁺, K⁺, and sometimes Ca²⁺, whereas GlyRs and GABA_ARs are inhibitory receptors with an anion channel selective for Cl⁻ (22).

3.1. The Orthosteric Site and the Ion Channel

Before the advent of high-resolution [three-dimensional (3D)] structures of nAChRs in 2000, the principal functional sites of the receptor had been explored by affinity labeling and mutagenesis approaches. These experiments showed that the neurotransmitter or orthosteric binding site is in the ECD at the interface between subunits. Three regions from the principal subunit (loops A, B, and C) and four from the complementary subunit (loops D, E, F, and G) contribute to the binding pocket (25). Loops A (Tyr), B (Trp), C (two Tyr), and D (Trp) form an aromatic box or cage chelating the ammonium group of ACh with the tryptophan residue from loop B, establishing a direct cation- π interaction (26).

The ion channel function was initially explored with blockers that bind within the TMD and prevent ion fluxes by sterically occluding the channel pore (reviewed in 20, 27). Early affinity-labeling experiments with channel blockers such as chlorpromazine (28, 29) or trimethyl phenyl phosphonium (30) identified key residues within the M2 segment at positions 2', 6', 9', 13', and 20' for each subunit of the pentamer; the conventional prime numbering starts at zero after the universally conserved positively charged residue at the cytoplasmic end of the pore (reviewed in 24, 31). This showed that the same side of each M2 helix faces the ion pore and that the walls of the channel consist of pentameric rings of homologous amino acids. Three rings of negatively charged residues frame the amino acid clusters labeled by chlorpromazine and were found by single-channel recording to contribute to cation permeation (32, 33). Later on, using site-directed mutagenesis, the region composed of M2 and the short loop bridging M1 and M2 was identified as the one governing the selectivity of the channel for cations in nAChRs and anions in GlyRs (34). This allowed the location of the selectivity filter of nAChRs to be determined; it is located at the cytoplasmic entrance of the pore, where a ring of glutamates at position -1' directly interacts with and selects for cations while repelling anions.

3.2. The Allosteric Modulatory Sites

An important outcome of the research on the allosteric properties of nAChRs (and pLGICs more generally) has been the discovery of diverse categories of modulatory sites with positive or negative effects on the signal transduction mechanism. These modulatory sites are referred to as allosteric in the sense that they are topographically distinct from the orthosteric site and modulate channel gating indirectly. Benzodiazepines, currently the most commonly prescribed psychoactive drugs, were the first allosteric modulators of pLGICs ever described. They modulate GABA_ARs (35, 36) by binding to allosteric sites located in the synaptic ECD (37, 38). Ca²⁺ ions were the first positive allosteric modulator (PAM) recognized for nAChRs (39, 40). They bind to a region distinct

from the ion channel (see Section 4) near the interface between the ECD and TMD (41, 42). Several hydrophobic molecules that bind to the TMD were found to display robust allosteric effects. First, the TMD is embedded in the lipid bilayer, and specific lipids including cholesterol and anionic lipids are required for proper function of the Torpedo nAChR. However, it is not clear yet whether lipids alter the structure and function of nAChRs through binding to allosteric sites or by altering bulk membrane physical properties (for recent reviews on nAChR–lipid interactions, see 43, 44). Small amphipathic compounds including short-chain alcohols and general anesthetics typically inhibit nAChRs and potentiate the inhibitory GlyRs and GABA_ARs, both of which contribute to anesthesia (45). The anthelmintic ivermectin (IVM), first discovered by Ōmura (157) and Campbell (46), is a PAM at $\alpha 7$ -nAChR (47) but also a PAM at the worm inhibitory receptors GluCl, where it enhances muscle inhibition and promotes worm paralysis, and GlyR (48). PAMs of nAChRs include a variety of natural and synthetic compounds (49) that have been subdivided into two groups. Those that increase the ACh (and nicotinic agonists) activation peak current with little or no effect on desensitization are referred to as type I. Those that delay and slow down the desensitization kinetics and, in some cases, even reactivate previously desensitized receptors are referred to as type II (50). IVM (47) and 5-hydroxyindole (51) are typical type-I PAMs at $\alpha 7$ nAChRs, whereas synthetic compounds like PNU-120596 (PNU) (52) or TQS (53) are type II. These compounds can act directly by binding to allosteric sites, indirectly by displacing already bound lipids, or in combination by using both mechanisms. Positive and negative modulators of nAChRs have been recently curated in a database named the Nicotinic Acetylcholine Receptor Allosteric Ligand Library (ACRALL) (54).

In addition, nAChRs are allosterically modulated by intracellular factors. The ICD carries several phosphorylation sites that modulate desensitization (55). For the muscle-type nAChR, the ICD binds tightly to rapsyn, a scaffolding protein that contributes to the stabilization and aggregation of receptors at the neuromuscular junction (56, 57). Growing evidence also suggests that $\alpha 7$ -nAChR binds to G proteins and may even mediate an agonist-elicited metabotropic function through stabilization of the desensitized state (58, 59).

4. HIGH-RESOLUTION STRUCTURES

4.1. Overall Molecular Architecture

Early structural data on nAChRs were obtained by processing electron microscopy (EM) images of purified proteins from *Electrophorus electricus* and AChR-rich membranes from *Torpedo marmorata* (60–62). The images revealed ring-like particles (8–9 nm in diameter) with a hydrophilic central core (approximately 1.5 nm) surrounded by a compact bundle made up of several (approximately five) subunits. Following the discovery that AChRs may form closely packed two-dimensional assemblies in *T. marmorata* postsynaptic membranes (63), substantial enhancement of map quality up to 4 Å was achieved (64, 65) but without reaching atomic resolution. The first bona fide models of the ACh-binding domain and binding site came from crystallographic studies of the ACh-binding protein (AChBP) (66), a water-soluble homolog of nAChR that is devoid of the TMD and occurs naturally in some invertebrates but without the conformational changes that mediate the receptor's activation.

For decades nAChRs from fish electric organs resisted crystallization. The discovery of prokaryotic homologs in bacteria (67, 68) revealed an unanticipated subfamily with a wide range of functional properties that were amenable to X-ray crystallography. The GABA-gated ELIC from *Erwinia chrysanthemi* was first solved in a closed-channel conformation (69). The proton-gated GLIC from *Gloeobacter violaceus* was then solved in both closed- and open-channel conformations (70–72), providing the first insights into the conformational changes mediating signal

transduction. Recently, other bacterial pLGICs have been solved, including the high-pH-gated STELIC from *Tevnia jerichonana* (73) and DeCLIC from *Desulfofustis deltaproteobacterium*, the first pentameric channel naturally fused to a periplasmic domain (74).

Riding the wave of success in bacteria, eukaryotic pLGICs were finally solved by X-ray crystallography, starting with the GluCl receptor from invertebrates (75) and followed in chronological order by GlyR (76), GABA_AR (77), 5HT₃R (78), and the first nAChR (79). Most recently, and thanks to several improvements in cryo-EM detectors and ad hoc measures to enhance protein expression, biochemical stability, and particle alignment, several high-resolution structures of nAChRs have been deposited (80). At the time of this review, 27 high-resolution structures of integral membrane nAChRs are available in the Protein Data Bank (PDB) (Table 1). These include the heteromeric muscle-type $\alpha\beta\gamma\delta$ and the homomeric neuronal $\alpha 7$ nAChRs in multiple states, and the heteromeric ganglionic $\alpha 3\beta 4$ and neuronal $\alpha 4\beta 2$ nAChRs in a single state.

Overall, the structural data collected so far point to a striking conservation of the molecular architecture of pLGICs from bacteria to mammals. The 3D structures illuminate both symmetrical and pseudosymmetrical organizations made of five identical or homologous subunits. Each subunit is modular and consists of a 190–200-amino-acid ECD organized in a β -sandwich including inner and outer β -sheets and a TMD composed of four α -helices (M1–M4). In agreement with biochemical studies (see Section 3), the M2 α -helices line the ion pore and interact with M1 and M3 that in turn interact with M4, which is located at the periphery of the protein and most exposed to lipids. In the eukaryotic receptors, a third ICD made of two α -helices (MX and MA) provides a platform for intracellular regulation (Figure 1).

4.2. Ligand-Binding Sites and Conformational Transitions at Atomic Resolution

High-resolution structures of nAChRs provide a detailed 3D description of the binding pockets of key classes of effectors as well as the conformational transitions they promote. In the following subsections, we present the details of the orthosteric site, the ion transmitter pore, and the allosteric binding sites that are emerging from the currently available structures.

4.2.1. The orthosteric site. Agonist-bound structures solved in complex with carbamylcholine; the natural alkaloids nicotine and epibatidine; and synthetic ligands like varenicline, encenicline (EVP-6124), and AT-1001 illuminate the details of agonist binding. Consistent with the biochemical data (see Section 3), these structures show that the agonist-binding site lies at the interface between subunits in the ECD. All agonists bear a key electropositive ammonium moiety that is stabilized by hydrogen bonding and characteristic cation– π interactions with the cage of five aromatic residues first identified by affinity labeling (81–83; reviewed in 14). A second key pharmacophore is an H-bond acceptor that interacts directly or via a bridging water molecule (84) with a main chain H-bond donor from loop E of the complementary subunit. In addition, high-resolution structures of the heteromeric $\alpha 4\beta 2$ and $\alpha 3\beta 4$ nAChRs show that the guanidinium group of an arginine from loop B of both the $\beta 2$ and $\beta 4$ subunits engages in cation– π interactions with two tyrosines of the aromatic cage, thus occupying the ammonium binding site (79, 84). This observation highlights that the orthosteric sites of heteromeric receptors are not equivalent and explains why orthosteric ligands bind to the α – β interface and not to the β – α or β – β interfaces in $\alpha 3\beta 4$ and $\alpha 4\beta 2$ nAChRs.

Competitive antagonist-bound structures including snake toxins (85–87), the active component of curare (88), and synthetic neuromuscular blockers (89) illuminate the details of the orthosteric site in the inhibited state(s) of the receptor. Compared to the agonist-bound state, most structures display a less compact ECD with a C-loop stabilized in a splayed-open conformation like

Table 1 High-resolution structure of nAChRs deposited in the Protein Data Bank

Type	Ligand	Other ligand(s)	Modulator(s)	State	PDB ID	Organism	Resolution (Å)	Reference
$\alpha\beta\gamma\delta$	Apo	Lipids	None	R	7QKO	<i>Tetronarce californica</i>	2.9	91
$\alpha\beta\gamma\delta$	Carbamylcholine	None	Agonist	D	7QL6	<i>Tetronarce californica</i>	3.2	91
$\alpha\beta\gamma\delta$	<i>d</i> -Tubocurarine	<i>d</i> -Tubocurarine Lipids Cholesterol	Antagonist	D	7SMS	<i>Tetronarce californica</i>	3.18	88
$\alpha\beta\gamma\delta$	Carbamylcholine	Lipids Cholesterol	Agonist	D	7SMR	<i>Tetronarce californica</i>	2.83	88
$\alpha\beta\gamma\delta$	Carbamylcholine	<i>d</i> -Tubocurarine Lipids Cholesterol	Agonist/anta	D	7SMT	<i>Tetronarce californica</i>	2.61	88
$\alpha\beta\gamma\delta$	α -Bungarotoxin	Lipids	Antagonist	R	6UWZ	<i>Tetronarce californica</i>	2.69	85
$\alpha\beta\gamma\delta$	Nicotine	Lipids	Agonist	D	7QL5	<i>Tetronarce californica</i>	2.5	91
$\alpha\beta\gamma\delta$	Apo	Lipids Cholesterol	None	R	7SMH	<i>Tetronarce californica</i>	2.57	88
$\alpha\beta\gamma\delta$	Apo	Lipids Cholesterol	None	R	7SMQ	<i>Tetronarce californica</i>	2.82	88
$\alpha\beta\gamma\delta$	Short-chain α -neurotoxin	None	Antagonist	R	7Z14	<i>Tetronarce californica</i>	3.15	86
$\alpha\beta\gamma\delta$	Rocuronium	Lipids Cholesterol	Antagonist	R	8ESK	<i>Tetronarce californica</i>	2.90	89
$\alpha\beta\gamma\delta$	Rocuronium	Rocuronium Lipids Cholesterol	Antagonist	R	8F2S	<i>Tetronarce californica</i>	2.90	89
$\alpha\beta\gamma\delta$	Choline	Etomidate Lipids Cholesterol	Agonist/NAM	D	8F6Y	<i>Tetronarce californica</i>	2.79	89
$\alpha\beta\gamma\delta$	Succinylcholine	Lipids Cholesterol	Antagonist	D	8F6Z	<i>Tetronarce californica</i>	2.70	89
$\alpha 7$	Encenicline	Cholesterol	Agonist	D	7EKP	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	2.85	90

(Continued)

Table 1 (Continued)

Type	Ligand	Other ligand(s)	Modulator(s)	State	PDB ID	Organism	Resolution (Å)	Reference
$\alpha 7$	Apo	Cholesterol	None	R	7EKI	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	3.18	90
$\alpha 7$	Encenicline	PNU-120596 Cholesterol	Agonist/PAM	D-open	7EKT	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	3.02	90
$\alpha 7$	Epibatidine	Ca ²⁺	Agonist	D	7KOQ	<i>Homo sapiens</i> / <i>Escherichia coli</i>	3.6	87
$\alpha 7$	Epibatidine	Ca ²⁺ PNU-120596 (?)	Agonist/PAM	A	7KOX	<i>Homo sapiens</i> / <i>Escherichia coli</i>	2.7	87
$\alpha 7$	α -Bungarotoxin	Ca ²⁺	Antagonist	R	7KOO	<i>Homo sapiens</i> / <i>Escherichia coli</i>	3	87
$\alpha 7$ (ECD)	Apo	C4	None	R	8C9X	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	2.46	104
$\alpha 7$ (ECD)	Nicotine	C4	Agonist/PAM	A/D-like	8CAU	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	3.51	104
$\alpha 7$ (ECD)	Apo	C4	None	R	8C12	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	3.4	104
$\alpha 7$ (ECD)	Apo	E3	Agonist/PAM	A/D-like	8CE4	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	2.53	104
$\alpha 7$ (ECD)	Nicotine	E3	Agonist/PAM	A/D-like	8C11	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	2.7	104
$\alpha 7$ (TMD+ICD)	Apo	None	None	R	7RPM	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	NMR	101
$\alpha 7$ (TMD+ICD)	Ivermectin	None	Agonist	D	8F4V	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	NMR	103
$\alpha 4\beta 2$	Varenicline	None	Agonist	D	6UR8	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	3.71	153
$\alpha 4\beta 2$	Varenicline	BAK5	Agonist	D	6USF	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	3.87	153
$\alpha 4\beta 2$ (2 α :3 β)	Nicotine	Cholesterol hemisuccinate	Agonist	D	6CNJ	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	3.7	154
$\alpha 4\beta 2$ (3 α :2 β)	Nicotine	Cholesterol hemisuccinate	Agonist	D	6CNK	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	3.9	154
$\alpha 4\beta 2$	Nicotine	None	Agonist	D	5KXI	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	3.94	79
$\alpha 3\beta 4$	AT-1001	Cholesterol hemisuccinate	Partial agonist	D	6PV8	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	3.87	84
$\alpha 3\beta 4$	Nicotine	Cholesterol hemisuccinate	Agonist	D	6PV7	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	3.34	84

Abbreviations: A, active, fast, open-channel state; D, slow desensitized state; ECD, extracellular domain; ICD, intracellular domain; NMR, nuclear magnetic resonance; PDB ID, Protein Data Bank identifier; R, resting closed-channel state; TMD, transmembrane domain.

Figure 1

The molecular architecture of the nAChR. For illustration purposes, the high-resolution structure of the muscle-type nAChR solved in complex with nicotine (PDB ID: 7QL5) is shown. The protein is represented as a ribbon diagram, and the lipid membrane as a gray box. One of the two α -subunits is highlighted in light blue. The structural features discussed in Section 4 are highlighted, namely, the orthosteric site with nicotine bound (*turquoise*), the $\beta 1$ - $\beta 2$ loop (*green*), loop C (*red*), loop F (*orange*), the Cys-loop (*magenta*), the M2-M3 linker (*dark blue*), and the MX helix (*yellow*). (a) Side view. The ECD, the TMD, and the ICD of the receptor are visualized. (b) Top view. The pentameric organization and the structure of the TMD are shown. The five leucine residues on the pore-lining M2 helices at the activation gate (i.e., Leu 9') are shown in stick form. Abbreviations: ECD, extracellular domain; ICD, intracellular domain; nAChR, nicotinic acetylcholine receptor; TMD, transmembrane domain.

the one found in the absence of ligands (the apo state) (88, 90, 91). With rocuronium, the additional volume is occupied by the ligand, which is larger and bulkier than any known agonist. In the α -toxin-bound structures, this volume is occupied by finger II of the toxin, which inserts and penetrates deeply into the orthosteric pocket. An arginine and a phenylalanine from α -Bgtx or a histidine from the short-chain α -neurotoxin stack in a cation- π sandwich with the highly conserved tyrosine from loop C (85-87). Altogether, the structural data suggest that bulky competitive antagonists stabilize an inhibited conformation of the receptors by preventing C-loop capping at the orthosteric site and compaction of the ECD. In sharp contrast, structures solved with depolarizing muscle blockers, like succinylcholine (89) or *d*-tubocurarine (*d*-tubo) (88), feature a fully closed or semiclosed C-loop in a configuration resembling that found with agonists. Consistent with functional experiments showing that large antagonists stabilize the resting state

(92) whereas smaller antagonists enhance desensitization (93), the structural data suggest that substances like curare and depolarizing muscle blockers would promote receptor inhibition by acting as desensitizers.

4.2.2. The ion pore. The active site of nAChRs is arguably the ion transmembrane pore that opens and closes in response to agonist binding. In agreement with early biochemical data (see Section 3), high-resolution structures of nAChRs demonstrate that the ion transmembrane pore is formed by the M2 helices at the pentameric axis of symmetry. Based on the pore configuration, the available structures can be roughly divided into two groups: (a) Those with no ligand (the apo state) or with large antagonists bound at the orthosteric site feature a straight orientation of the M2 helices that produces a hydrophobic constriction in the middle of the membrane at positions 9', 13', and 16' and (b) those with an agonist bound feature tilted M2 helices with a constriction point near the cytosol formed by five glutamates at position -1'. The permeability of these conformations to both ions and water has been tentatively assigned based on static measurements of the pore diameter using software tools like HOLE (94) or CHAP (95) (see Section 5.1). Since both classes feature a minimum pore diameter that is smaller than the size of partially hydrated cations (e.g., Na⁺), all structures were annotated as nonconductive. In addition, the strong hydrophobic character at the constriction point of the apo-like structures appears inconsistent with the translocation of ions and possibly water, and these structures can be reasonably assigned to the resting state. Such hydrophobic gating (96) in the middle of the pore has been consistently observed in all pLGICs. By contrast, in the agonist-bound structures, the constriction is formed by a ring of negatively charged residues on the cytosolic side of the TMD whose side chains can plausibly adapt to a cation, allowing for chelation and possibly translocation. The cryo-EM densities of $\alpha 4\beta 2$ and $\alpha 3\beta 4$ bound to nicotine indicate that these glutamates at position -1' likely coordinate a monovalent cation, which was proposed to prevent cation permeation by electrostatic repulsion (84). Based on these considerations, all agonist-bound structures, together with those in complex with small antagonists like succinylcholine or *d*-tubo, were annotated as desensitized states. Consistent with this conclusion, anionic pLGICs with agonist bound feature a similar conformation of the ion pore with a hydrophobic constriction near the cytosol (97). However, one cannot rule out the hypothesis that the desensitization gate is located differently at nAChRs, e.g., at position 9' as suggested by recent simulations of $\alpha 7$ -nAChR (98), and that the surprising organization of the five glutamates at the bottom of the TMD is physiologically irrelevant.

Two structures of $\alpha 7$ -nAChR recently solved by cryo-EM in the presence of agonist and a large excess of PNU (87, 90) illuminated a distinct organization of the ion channel. Interestingly, the cryo-EM densities indicate that PNU binding causes significant widening of the ion pore in the middle of the TMD, mostly due to the rearrangement of the L9' side chains that rotate out of the pore axis. Since PNU is a type-II PAM of $\alpha 7$ that is able to reactivate previously desensitized receptors (49), the structures in the presence of agonist and an excess of PNU were tentatively assigned to the activated state of the receptor (87) and a partially desensitized or partially open state (90), respectively. Although these structures are suggestive and reminiscent of the cryo-EM of 5HT₃R solved under activating conditions (99), their relevance remains unclear. In particular, the structure of the supposedly active state of $\alpha 7$ -nAChR shows a surprising compression (by 5–10 Å) of the TMD in the direction perpendicular to the membrane, and this is not observed in the R state (before activation) or the D state (after activation). Such a compression results in significant tilting of the TM helices along with vertical sliding of the M4 helix, which produces partial helical unwinding at the M4–MA junction. These energetically costly rearrangements were proposed to mediate ion permeation via the widening of lateral fenestrations in the ICD (87). However, recent simulation analyses have shown that ions may freely diffuse to the intracellular vestibule through

these portals even in structures with intact M4–MA junctions (98). Given the peculiarity of the PNU-bound structures, more studies are needed to assess their physiological significance.

At the limit of functional annotations based on static structures, the data collected at nAChR indicate that in the R state, the ion channel is closed by a patch of bulky hydrophobic residues in the middle of M2 (the activation gate), whereas the location of the desensitization gate remains debated.

4.2.3. The intracellular domain. The ICD plays a critical role in pentameric assembly, trafficking, subcellular localization, allosteric signaling, and channel conductance (22, 100). Following the seminal work of Gharpure et al. on $\alpha 3\beta 4$ (84), several high-resolution structures of the ICD in nAChRs have been obtained. The structural data indicate that each subunit contributes to the ICD with a short post-M3 loop, a short amphipathic MX helix that lies parallel to the membrane plane, a poorly conserved and disordered cytoplasmic loop named loop L, and a long MA helix that protrudes ~ 40 Å into the cytosol. These helices form a pentameric bundle that frames five lateral portals for ion permeation. These portals are lined by both acidic and polar residues that provide a favorable environment for cation permeation, and charge reversal at these sites was shown to attenuate the single-channel conductance (84). Perhaps surprisingly, the MA-helical bundle does not undergo major conformational changes in the agonist-bound versus antagonist-bound structures (88) with the lateral fenestrations being large enough (8–12 Å) to allow for the permeation of hydrated cations even in the resting state (85). Strikingly, the poorly conserved L-loop is not solved in any of the high-resolution structures of intact nAChRs. Recently, Bondarenko et al. (101) modeled the structure of a smaller, functional construct encompassing the TMD and ICD of the human $\alpha 7$ -nAChR using structure restraints from nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) and electron spin resonance spectroscopy. This structure offered the first glimpse of the 3D architecture of the ICD including loop L, which appears to harbor three short helical segments that adopt a characteristic B shape. The large fraction of formally charged residues (18 pairs) unevenly distributed along the sequence results in regions with a net positive charge in the upper ICD that interact with lipids from the inner leaflet and regions with a net negative charge in the lower ICD that likely bind cytoplasmic partners.

4.2.4. The allosteric binding site(s). The currently available structures illuminate five allosteric sites at nAChRs with atomic resolution, in addition to several lipid-binding sites (**Figure 2**). The structure of $\alpha 7$ -nAChR with PNU bound illuminates the details of an intersubunit allosteric site in the TMD (90). In this structure, PNU inserts deeply at the interface between subunits, forming interactions with M2 and M3 from the (+)-subunit and M1 and M2 from the (–)-subunit. This modulatory site is located on the extracellular side of the TMD and strongly overlaps with the IVM-binding site first illuminated with GluCl (75) and GlyR (76, 102). The recent NMR structure of a TMD+ICD functional construct from $\alpha 7$ -nAChR, which is activated by IVM, provides evidence that IVM binds to the same intersubunit allosteric site as PNU, albeit more superficially (103). Since IVM is a type-I PAM of $\alpha 7$ -nAChR (47), the structural data suggest that the depth of ligand insertion may be critical for the modulation of desensitization.

The structure of the muscle-type nAChR in complex with the antagonist *d*-tubo shows toxin density in two unexpected allosteric sites in addition to the classical orthosteric sites (88). In this structure, *d*-tubo binds at both the extracellular entrance of the ion pore and the periphery of the TMD at the junction between M1, M3, and M4 (**Figure 2**). Interestingly, in the latter binding mode, *d*-tubo appears to stabilize a detached conformation of the M4 helix, which moves away from the receptor core. Since a similar uncoupling of M4 was proposed to lead to slower recovery from desensitization (88), both the peripheral and the pore-blocking binding sites are potential sites for negative allosteric modulation. Consistently, a similar intrasubunit site with a detached M4

Figure 2

The orthosteric and allosteric ligand-binding sites at nAChR illuminated by high-resolution structures of intact receptors. (a) The structure of the muscle nAChR in complex with α -bungarotoxin (PDB ID: 6UWZ). (b) The structure of $\alpha 7$ -AChR solved in complex with the orthosteric agonist encenicline (not shown) and the type-II PAM PNU (PDB ID: 7EKT). These two structures are representative of the resting and desensitized states of nAChRs, respectively. Coordinates of the modulatory compounds (*d*-tubocurarine is shown in teal, etomidate in pink, PNU in red, and ivermectin in yellow) were extracted from corresponding high-resolution structures upon optimal superimposition of the protein. As discussed in Section 4.2.1, competitive antagonists like snake toxins and neuromuscular blockers (e.g., rocuronium) bind to the ECD in the resting state. Agonists (e.g., acetylcholine, nicotine), competitive antagonists enhancing desensitization (e.g., *d*-tubocurarine), PAMs targeting the ECD (e.g., nanobodies), the TMD (e.g., PNU or ivermectin) or the ECD–TMD interface (e.g., calcium ions), and NAMs (e.g., etomidate) bind preferentially to either the active or the desensitized states. Abbreviations: ECD, extracellular domain; ICD, intracellular domain; nAChR, nicotinic acetylcholine receptor; NAM, negative allosteric modulator; PAM, positive allosteric modulator; PDB ID, Protein Data Bank identifier; PNU, PNU-120596; TMD, transmembrane domain.

was found in the cryo-EM structure of the muscle nAChR in complex with the general anesthetic etomidate (89). We note in passing that numerous cryo-EM structures of the muscle nAChR show electron densities allowing partial construction of lipids, including cholesterol and phospholipids, bound at the interface between the receptor and the lipid bilayer. However, depending on the biochemical preparation, these lipids are found at somewhat different locations and in different poses in the grooves between the TMD helices. The contribution of each lipid-binding site to allosteric modulation remains at present unclear (for a recent review, see 43).

Recent cryo-EM studies of $\alpha 7$ -nAChR illuminated the details of the regulatory site for calcium in the ECD (87) and revealed a novel intersubunit allosteric site at the apex of the ECD (104). In agreement with early biochemical studies, the cryo-EM structures of $\alpha 7$ -nAChR in complex with

calcium ions revealed strong ball-shaped densities in proximity to the $\beta 1$ – $\beta 2$ loop and the Cys-loop, consistent with calcium binding at the ECD–TMD interface (87) (**Figure 2**). These motifs carry glutamate residues whose mutation abolishes calcium potentiation (41) and were annotated as PAM binding sites. Interestingly, homologs of the Ca^{2+} -binding sites have been characterized with the bacterial channel ELIC, for which divalent cations including Ba^{2+} behave as negative modulators (105). Most recently, the structure of the $\alpha 7$ -nAChR ECD was solved in complex with two allosteric nanobodies (104), obtained through immunization of alpacas to generate highly potent and $\alpha 7$ -specific modulators (106). This previously unrecognized allosteric site is located at the apex of the pentameric architecture lined by the long $\beta 2$ – $\beta 3$ loop, aka the main immunogenic region, and the top α -helices from both the principal and complementary subunits. The high-resolution structures of the complex reveal a symmetric pentameric assembly of the nanobodies that extends the ECD similar to the regulatory N-terminal domain in homologous receptors (74) (**Figure 2**).

Altogether, the recent cryo-EM analyses of nAChRs illuminate the details of five allosteric ligand-binding sites scattered along the protein structure. Given the large size of the receptor, other modulatory sites likely remain to be characterized. Sites that are currently missing include those identified in other pLGICs, such as benzodiazepine sites at the nonorthosteric interfaces of GABA_ARs (37, 107, 108), sites directly above the orthosteric site (109) or on the vestibular side of the orthosteric site (110), and TMD sites like the intrasubunit site for general anesthetics found in GLIC (45).

5. MECHANISMS OF ACTIVATION AND DESENSITIZATION

The conformational transitions between the physiological states of the receptor involve a global reorganization of the protein that can be spontaneous or stabilized by effector binding. The characterization of these conformational changes with atomic resolution is challenging since it potentially involves a multitude of transient conformations. Moreover, nAChRs have been fine-tuned to achieve signal transduction on a submillisecond timescale, as shown in fast-perfused outside-out patch clamp recordings (111), which makes them challenging to probe by direct functional assays. In addition, experimental structural determinations with atomic resolution illuminate receptors in states that are often stabilized in nonphysiological conditions, i.e., trapped in crystals or frozen in thin vitreous ice with the lipid membrane replaced by detergent micelles or lipid nanodiscs. In this context, time-resolved analyses generated by computer simulations and/or functional assays, e.g., involving the incorporation of fluorescent probes, can go beyond structures to provide mechanistic insights in physiologically relevant conditions.

5.1. Functional Annotation of Structures

The functional annotation of ion-channel structures from X-ray crystallography and cryo-EM is difficult, albeit essential. As previously discussed, extrapolations of channel permeability from geometric analyses of the pore are limited and cannot account for protein–buffer and protein–membrane interactions, nor for the conformational dynamics of the protein. To overcome these limitations, specialized simulation approaches have been developed. Assuming that pore hydration can be used as a proxy for channel conductance, Trick et al. (112) proposed a functional annotation of ion-channel structures based on analysis of the water density inside the pore. Alternatively, pore permeability can be probed by single-ion free energy profile calculations based on umbrella sampling (112) or enhanced sampling simulations (98). Although computationally more involved, these calculations provide information on the energetics and selectivity of ion permeation. More recently, molecular dynamics (MD) simulations with voltage applied were used to predict the

channel conductance and selectivity by counting the number of ion-translocation events in finite time windows, a method called *in silico* electrophysiology (113). In the case of GlyR, such analyses predicted that an early cryo-EM structure of a presumed active state solved in detergents (76) was fivefold more conductive for Cl⁻ relative to experiments and was nonselective for polyatomic anions (113). Remarkably, the relaxation of this wide-open state by MD simulations in a lipid bilayer yielded a narrower open-channel state that recapitulated the permeability properties by electrophysiology (113, 114). This open-channel structure was experimentally validated by subsequent cryo-EM studies of GlyR in a native-like lipid environment (115). Most recently, computational electrophysiology combined with single-channel recordings and site-directed mutagenesis revealed the existence of lateral fenestrations for Cl⁻ translocation in the ECD of GlyR, which explains the origin of current rectification in known anomalous mutants (116).

In nAChRs, MD analyses of high-resolution structures have started to provide additional insights. For example, the agonist-bound structures of $\alpha 3\beta 4$ and $\alpha \beta \gamma \delta$ initially annotated as desensitized were found to contain a fully hydrated pore in both backbone-restrained (91) and unrestrained (84) simulations, somewhat suggestive of an ion-conductive channel. Simulation studies of $\alpha 7$ by all-atom MD, ion-permeation free energy profiles, and *in silico* electrophysiology provided evidence that the structure in complex with α -Bgtx is nonconductive, the one solved with agonist plus PNU is conductive and cation selective, and the one solved with agonist alone is nonconductive and plausibly represents the desensitized state (98). Interestingly, and in contrast with previous conclusions, these analyses suggest that the desensitization gate may be located at the hydrophobic girdle at position 9', somewhat overlapping with the activation gate (98). Considering the gap between static structures frozen in detergents and membrane-inserted functional receptors, additional simulation analyses are needed to provide further mechanistic insights.

5.2. The Mechanism of Ion-Channel Activation with Atomic Resolution

The classical MWC interpretation of ion-channel activation or gating in nAChRs is based on an equilibrium model that does not aim to describe the trajectory connecting the end states of the transition. However, the mechanism underlying signal transduction involves a dynamic process between these states, whose details have been explored for more than 50 years. Computational analyses based on all-atom MD have been used extensively to break through the dynamic nature of the phenomenon and shed light onto the sequence of structural events translating neurotransmitter binding into pore opening. Early studies based on homology models of $\alpha 7$ and short unbiased MD (117) or targeted MD (118) simulations highlighted a strong correlation between closing of the C-loop at the orthosteric site and opening of the activation gate via twisting of subunits in the ECD and tilting of the M2 helices in the TMD. Simulation work on the X-ray structures of GLIC (119) and GluCl (120, 121) with agonist removed (i.e., ungating) provided evidence for an indirect coupling between agonist binding and pore opening, suggesting that global receptor twisting elicited by agonist unbinding would lock the channel in a nonactivatable resting state. In addition, these studies predicted that a global expansion of the ECD, referred to as blooming, is a key element of the allosteric mechanism, which was later confirmed by the X-ray structures of GLIC and GluCl solved in the absence of agonist (72, 122). By modeling agonist binding in the resting state of 5HT₃R and MD relaxation, the gating mechanism was also probed in the forward direction (123). The simulations revealed that the structural stress introduced by ligand binding at the orthosteric site could be released via contraction of the ECD (i.e., un-blooming) and repositioning of loops at the ECD-TMD interface (i.e., M2-M3, $\beta 1\beta 2$, and the Cys-loop) that promote the stabilization of a water-permeable ion pore via tilting of M2, M3, and the interconnecting loop. Interestingly, these simulations first suggested that ion permeation would require a conformational switch of two rings of hydrophobic residues at the activation gate (i.e., L9' and V13') to

reduce steric hindrance (123). More recently, using the string method with swarms of trajectories, Lev et al. (124) provided a detailed model of activation in the proton-gated channel GLIC. Beyond accounting for the modulation by pH, this model of gating introduced a new mechanistic element highlighting the role of the contraction and expansion of the extracellular β -sandwiches at the ECD–TMD interface that was validated by fluorescence experiments (125). Only very recently, MD simulations were used to characterize the allosteric pathways in nAChRs (126). Using a large number of nonequilibrium MD trajectories, it was shown that agonist removal from the orthosteric site of a nicotine-bound $\alpha 4\beta 2$ nAChR produces an extremely fast wave of conformational rearrangements propagating from the C-loop to the M2–M3 linker at the ECD–TMD interface on a nanosecond timescale. Although these calculations are too short to capture the large amplitude changes underlying activation, they highlight the implication of loop F in the allosteric mechanism. Strikingly, the same communication pathway was also detected in $\alpha 7$ nAChR (127).

Altogether, the simulation analyses of nAChRs and homologs suggest that the transition from resting to active involves a series of discrete conformational changes that start at the level of the orthosteric site with C-loop closing and are transmitted and amplified via: (a) untilting of the extracellular subunits, which results in a global contraction or unblooming of the ECD; (b) repositioning of loops at the ECD–TMD interface; (c) the outward displacement of the M2–M3 linker coupled to tilting of the pore-lining M2 helices; and (d) opening of the activation gate via rotameric transitions of bulky and hydrophobic residues in the middle of M2 that promote pore wetting and ion permeation. The details of such a conformational wave translating agonist binding to pore opening are illustrated in **Figure 3a,b**. In addition, the simulation analyses indicate that the allosteric communication between the orthosteric site and the ion pore involves a weak coupling mechanism, where nearly autonomous quaternary changes at the ECD or TMD stabilized by ligand-binding events are communicated at the ECD–TMD interface via shape complementarity rather than specific residue–residue interactions. Here, weak refers to statistical coupling rather than mechanical coupling, which is typically referred to as strong in the field of molecular motors (128). Consistent with this idea, isolated ECDs and TMDs were shown to fold spontaneously when properly engineered (129, 130), and combinations of ECDs and TMDs from different receptor families often generate functional chimeras (131). This mechanism is also supported by aggressive mutagenesis studies at the ECD–TMD interface (132). A weak coupling mechanism for gating, which is reminiscent of the function of biomolecular motors (133) and artificial molecular nanomachines (134), naturally accounts for the occurrence of nonconducting intermediates on the way to activation, which are discussed in the next section.

5.3. The Multi-Step Transition Pathway of Activation

The MWC model was based upon discrete states in thermodynamic equilibrium and did not provide insights into the dynamics of their interconversion. The development of new technologies made this accessible. Among the biophysical methods to monitor protein motion, fluorescence studies via the covalent incorporation of conformation-sensitive dyes have the unique advantage of allowing for the investigation of receptors in purified but also cell-expressed environments. Voltage-clamp fluorometry (VCF), which probes fluorescent changes and electrophysiological currents simultaneously in real time, has been particularly successful in providing insights into the dynamics of conformational changes at intermediate states that are undetectable by electrophysiology. Labeling of the muscle nAChR ($\alpha\beta\gamma\delta$) at the top of the TMD (position 19', located at the upper end of M2, facing the ECD) reported a conformational change in a monoliganded receptor that does not involve channel opening and occurs with fast kinetics (135). A somewhat similar phenotype was described for the $\alpha 4\beta 4$ receptor labeled at the extracellular loop 5, which faces the vestibule, suggesting that ACh and the competitive antagonist dihydro- β -erythroidine

elicit movement of this region allosterically without activation (136). A related phenotype was observed and investigated in depth with GLIC (137) and $\alpha 1$ -GlyR (138). In addition, VCF of $\alpha 1$ -GlyR labeled at the ECD-TMD interface showed that the receptor transits through a cluster of intermediate states characterized by robust fluorescence variations but no currents (138).

(Caption appears on following page)

Figure 3 (Figure appears on preceding page)

The molecular mechanism of nAChR activation. (a) The conformational wave of gating, as derived from high-resolution structures and simulation studies. The sequence of structural events translating agonist binding into pore opening is shown from top to bottom. The structures of the muscle nAChR in the apo state (PDB ID: 7QKO; *white*) and in complex with nicotine (PDB ID: 7QL5; *cyan*) are shown to illustrate the conformational changes mediating channel activation. (i) Agonist (i.e., nicotine) binding to the ECD elicits a significant contraction of the orthosteric site characterized by a large displacement of the C-loop that closes over it. (ii) Closing of C-loop coupled to the global tilting of the extracellular β -sandwiches promotes the repositioning of several loops including $\beta 1\beta 2$, $\beta 8\beta 9$, and the Cys-loop, thus transmitting the signal to the ECD–TMD interface. (iii) These rearrangements facilitate the translation of the M2–M3 linker in the outward direction, which occurs with significant tilting of the pore-lining M2 helices. The resulting expansion of the ion pore, along with rotameric transitions of the bulky and hydrophobic residues that open the activation gate (i.e., L9'), promote pore wetting and ion permeation. (b) A diagram representation of the conformational wave shown in panel a. (c) The progressive mechanism of activation of nAChRs, highlighting intermediate conformations deduced from combined fluorescence and electrophysiological observations (preactive state) and from kinetic analysis of single-channel recordings (flipped or primed state). nAChRs are shown in simplified form as dimers, with the channel-lining M2 helices shown as orange cylinders. Abbreviations: ECD, extracellular domain; nAChR, nicotinic acetylcholine receptor; PDB ID, Protein Data Bank identifier; TMD, transmembrane domain. The diagram representation of the conformational wave shown in panel b was adapted with permission from Reference 91.

These intermediates are stabilized in different pharmacological conditions, including low Gly concentrations, saturating concentrations of the partial agonists taurine and β -alanine, and mixtures of the competitive antagonist strychnine and the agonist glycine. By contrast, the general anesthetic propofol, which binds to the TMD, destabilizes these intermediate states, favoring isomerization to the active conformation in the presence of agonist. MD simulations further showed that this atypical pharmacological profile is compatible with the contribution of clusters of conformations derived from a taurine-bound closed structure obtained by cryo-EM (115), which are characterized by high flexibility of the ECD and the orthosteric site. With GLIC, a preactivation phenotype was reported for a series of fluorescent sensors at the ECD and the M2–M3 loop at the ECD–TMD interface (137). In this case, preactivation mainly concerns a quaternary compaction of the ECD that precedes the reorganization of the ECD–TMD interface involving contraction of the extracellular β -sandwiches and tilting of the pore-lining M2 helices (125). Altogether, the fluorescence data point to an unanticipated structural plasticity of nAChRs and their homologs, which allows the formation of a dynamic intermediate state on the way to activation that features a marked asymmetric organization of the protein. These intermediate conformations, which are exacerbated in loss-of-function mutants, may contribute to the formation of transition pathways that are dead-ends, precluding channel opening, or transient states that precede activation.

A second family of late gating intermediates was inferred from kinetic analyses of single-channel recordings. Measurement of close-to-open transition kinetics and fitting using multistate models suggested that channel activation at GlyR and muscle nAChR both involve a transient population of short-lived intermediates named flipped (139) and primed (140). Notably, the allosteric equilibrium between flipped and active appears to be independent of the nature of the ligand bound at the orthosteric site, suggesting it is a late intermediate formed after the ECD has completed activation.

Overall, functional data from VCF and single-channel electrophysiology are consistent with a progressive propagation of the gating transition from the orthosteric site to the ion pore in the form of a conformational wave. The emerging mechanism involves distinct clusters of early (VCF) and late (single-channel electrophysiology) intermediate conformations that are undetectable by electrophysiology but contribute to the channel activation path (**Figure 3c**), thereby impacting the time course of the gating currents. Importantly, these intermediates underly the distinct actions of agonists, antagonists, and partial agonists and are likely relevant for drug discovery. We note that single-channel recordings of mutants of the muscle nAChR analyzed by REFERS (rate equilibrium linear free energy relationships) are consistent with an early motion of the ECD, especially of the

orthosteric site and the M2–M3 loop, and a late motion of the TMD during channel activation (141).

5.4. Toward a General Mechanism of Signal Transduction

The combination of high-resolution structures, *in silico* simulations, VCF, and single-channel recordings highlights common traits of the molecular mechanism(s) of signal transduction by nAChRs and receptor homologs. The long-range allosteric communication between the orthosteric site and the ion channel gate, which are >50 Å apart within the protein structure, does not imply an all-or-none concerted reorganization but rather a progressive conformational wave. The agonists stabilize a local perturbation at the orthosteric site that propagates from the ECD to the TMD. Along this path, the receptor visits several metastable intermediate conformations, especially when the propagating signal encounters the hinge at the ECD–TMD interface. Consistent with the MWC model, channel activation involves major quaternary reorganizations of the protein domains between discrete preexisting states, which are stabilized by ligand-binding events and communicated at the ECD–TMD interface via shape complementarity. The subunit interfaces, as well as the ECD–TMD interface, thus play a key role in signal propagation, starting from the C-loop and F-loop at the orthosteric site, to the M2–M3 loop that is directly connected to the pore-lining M2 helices. The emerging mechanism of activation appears to be conserved in virtually all pLGICs from bacteria to humans, with important consequences for the mode of action of allosteric effectors. By contrast, the mechanism of desensitization requires further investigation, and current models based on anionic pLGICs might not apply to nAChRs.

6. IMPLICATIONS FOR DRUG DISCOVERY

Besides the illumination of the conformational changes underlying activation and desensitization, the atomic structures of nAChRs provide 3D templates of the orthosteric site and several allosteric modulatory sites that can be used for drug design. In addition, it has been shown that within the limits of the MWC model, quantitative predictions of the pharmacological attributes of potency, efficacy, and selectivity of the modulatory ligands can be obtained from the ligand-binding affinities for the resting, active, and desensitized states of the receptor (142) (**Figure 4**). This offers a general theoretical framework for allosteric drug design at synaptic receptors, which we term state-based or conformation-specific pharmacology (142). Because ligand-binding affinities for discrete conformational states of nAChRs are difficult to measure experimentally, this framework for drug design is best suited for simulation analyses and binding free energy calculations.

Since the first high-resolution structures of AChBP, modeling approaches based on all-atom MD simulations have been used to obtain reliable binding free energy estimates for nicotinic ligands. Early studies with empirical free energy rescoring showed that agonists and antagonists could be correctly classified based on affinities estimated from docking on homology models of the open and closed states of $\alpha 4\beta 2$ nAChR (143). Simplified binding free energy calculations based on the molecular mechanics Poisson–Boltzmann surface area (MM/PBSA) method were shown to reproduce relative binding affinities for 16 known agonists and identify two novel $\alpha 7$ -selective agonists (144). Using quantum mechanical calculations on a model of the muscle nAChR, Beck et al. (145) explored the selectivity of nicotinoid and neonicotinoid ligands in human versus insect cells and explained why nicotine has limited efficacy as an insecticide. The rational design of potent and selective antagonists derived from α -conotoxins was achieved by *in silico* mutational scanning coupled to MM/PBSA free energy calculations, yielding new RegIIA variants selective for $\alpha 3\beta 2$ nAChR versus $\alpha 3\beta 4$ nAChR (146). Affinity predictions based on alchemical free energy perturbation (FEP) calculations for three α -conotoxins targeting $\alpha 3\beta 2$ nAChR but not $\alpha 3\beta 4$ nAChR were

Potency $EC_{50} = \frac{K_{d,O}}{\sqrt{L}}$

Efficacy $P_o^{\max} = \frac{L \left(\frac{K_{d,C}}{K_{d,O}}\right)^n}{1 + L \left(\frac{K_{d,C}}{K_{d,O}}\right)^n}$

Selectivity $K_{\alpha,\beta} = \frac{K_{d,O}(\alpha)}{K_{d,O}(\beta)} \sqrt{\frac{L_\beta}{L_\alpha}}$

Figure 4

Pharmacological attributes of the modulatory ligands as predicted by the Monod–Wyman–Changeux model. Assuming that the open (O) and closed (C) states of the ion channel preexist in reversible equilibrium in both the presence and absence of agonist (A), the model predicts that agonist potency (EC_{50}), efficacy (P_o^{\max}), and binding selectivity for α versus β can all be accessed from the ligand-binding affinities for the open ($1/K_{d,O}$) and closed ($1/K_{d,C}$) states of the receptor (142). The equations show that the pharmacological attributes depend on the unliganded gating constant (L) and the number of agonists bound (n). Abbreviations: A, agonist; C, closed; EC_{50} , half maximal effective concentration; $K_{d,C}$, dissociation constant of the closed state; $K_{d,O}$, dissociation constant of the open state; L , unliganded gating constant; L' , liganded gating constant; n , number of agonists bound; O, open.

shown to reproduce relative binding affinities and potencies for a series of single-point toxin mutants and were used to predict 52 $\alpha 3\beta 2$ -selective toxin mutations in quantitative agreement with experiments (147). Last, highly accurate binding affinity predictions were recently reported for nicotine in AChBP using alchemical FEP calculations (148). The excellent retrospective performance of rigorous binding free energy calculations for nAChRs puts the rational design of agonists and antagonists within reach. In this context, the growing number of nAChR structures unraveling unique conformational states of the receptor, including intermediates, are very appealing for the development of novel classes of potent and selective modulatory ligands.

7. CONCLUSION: A NOVEL ALLOSTERIC LANDSCAPE

The nAChR was the first neurotransmitter receptor isolated and biochemically identified as a homo- and heteropentameric membrane protein with a rotational axis of symmetry perpendicular to the plane of the membrane. Each individual subunit can be subdivided into three structural domains with distinct functions, i.e., an ECD, a TMD, and an ICD. Extensive early biochemical studies demonstrated that nAChR is a bona fide allosteric protein carrying multiple categories of topographically distinct, and conformationally linked, ligand-binding sites.

Thanks to the discovery of nAChR homologs in prokaryotes, the 3D atomic structures of the first ligand-gated ion channels have been established and subsequently found to be very similar to

other members of the nAChR superfamily, including the eukaryotic GluCl, GABA_A, glycine, and 5HT₃ receptors and, of course, several oligomeric subtypes of nAChRs. The structural studies at high resolution led to the description at the atomic level of the distinct categories of functional sites carried by these receptors and their variability. They include the orthosteric site(s) for the neurotransmitter and its homologs, the ion channel sites for channel blockers, and multiple allosteric modulatory sites distributed all over the protein with little or no structural homology with the orthosteric sites. These findings reveal a surprising bacterial phylogenetic origin for our brain receptors, plausibly imposing bottom-up constraints on the modulation of higher brain functions.

The fast (millisecond) conformational change of the protein, or allosteric transition, mediating activation of the ion channel by ACh or its homologs was initially identified biochemically by fluorescence spectroscopy, offering the first structural evidence for signal transduction beyond electrophysiological methods. The structural changes mediating activation have since been resolved at the atomic level for nAChR and its homologs using high-resolution X-ray and cryo-EM methods and MD simulations, together with careful assessments of pore opening in each ion-channel state. Globally, the data fit the MWC two-state model but with additional important peculiarities. Furthermore, simulation studies and joint fluorescence and patch-clamp analyses of the dynamics of the transition between the discrete resting and active conformations reveal a complex propagation of the conformational change involving a number of short-lived preactive intermediates.

Unlike classical allosteric proteins, nAChRs and their homologs spontaneously form multiple interconvertible conformations including slowly accessible (100 ms–1 sec) desensitized states, which have higher affinity for agonists and, most often, closed channels. Their structure at high resolution demonstrates striking differences from the resting and active conformations. The plausible role of desensitization in the regulation of synapse efficacy as well as the molecular mechanism underlying the transition from active to desensitized need to be further explored.

The recent results of joint MD and structural data on nAChRs and their homologs create a double paradigmatic change in our current understanding of the mode of action of pharmacological agents and drug design.

First, drug action can no longer be viewed as a competitive interaction taking place by steric hindrance at the level of a common, rigid, binding site (149, 150). Allosteric modulatory sites, which do not show any structural analogy with the orthosteric sites, efficiently regulate signal transduction and serve as novel, highly efficient targets, possibly with fewer side effects than orthosteric ligands. For instance, among the clinically used allosteric drugs (151), a postpartum depression treatment based on a positive allosteric modulator of GABA_AR, brexanolone, has been recently approved by the FDA (Zulresso[®]) (152).

Second, the detailed structural and functional identification of the several conformational states of nAChR and its homologs at the atomic level paves the way for a new conformation-specific pharmacology, resulting in the deliberate design of agonists, antagonists, and desensitizing agents. This is of major importance for pharmacological therapeutics targeting the abundant neuropsychiatric disorders driven by nAChR (and its homologs). Applications include, among others, cognitive enhancement, nicotine addiction, learning and memory, neuroinflammation, schizophrenia, epilepsy, degenerative diseases like Alzheimer's and Parkinson's, and also aging.

The data and perspectives presented here further illustrate the critical role played over the past several decades by nAChR as a structural and functional model for neurotransmitter receptors with important consequences for drug design and therapeutics for neuropsychiatric deficits.

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